

PECULIARITIES OF RELATIONS IN FAMILIES OF INTER-ETHNIC MARRIAGES

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Family and marriage are social institutions in which all people on earth participate. Everyone is included in them in one way or another, or at least has a relationship with them. We know that the foundations of personal relations with representatives of other ethnic communities are laid in the family, and many things in people's lives depend on how these relations will be. A person is the bearer of the traditions and customs, social and moral values of the nation to which he belongs from his youth. But if the family is multi-ethnic, the process of formation, absorption and preservation of skills, traditions, etc. is not clear at all.

Relationships in families where people from different ethnic communities live together certainly have their own characteristics, which can be seen in the following:

- the influence of national psychological characteristics on the development of common solutions, specific characteristics of educational effects on the nature of interpersonal relations between spouses, children and other family members during cohabitation, mutual relations and communication;

- in families where parents are representatives of different nationalities, unique spiritual and moral, possibly religious values, behavior and forms of activity, traditions with a unique perception and understanding of the world, and the national identity of the individual existence and activity of national differences in ways of forming identity;

- factors and causes of conflict between members of different ethnic families.

Both the readiness to marry and the desire to start a family - all this shows that people understand the importance of family relationships, obligations to each other, responsibility for the future of the family and children, voluntary acceptance of inevitable problems and limitations of personal freedom. These features have their own national expression. Every nation has its own traditions, values, and culture. Each ethnic group develops its own ideas about what these characteristics should be and strives to preserve them in the national consciousness, traditions, actions and attitudes of its people.

Each ethnic group has its own laws and principles, such as:

- initial acquaintance with family life, its psychology (from birth) and formation of general ideas about it, especially if the people getting married are representatives of different ethnic communities;
- forming views on one's family as multi-ethnic;
- implementing their own ideas about a multi-ethnic family in marriage;
- gathering experience of family life in a multinational environment;
- further improvement of family relations in the process of strengthening marital ties.

Naturally, if the spouses are representatives of different nations, often everything is not smooth, many difficulties arise related to the specific characteristics of the national dignity of each of them. This is a difficult and even dangerous period of marriage (from the point of view of stability), any quarrels, and especially those colored by ethnic characteristics, can drive people away from each other. But let's not forget about love.

After the birth of a child, a change of roles, emergence of parental responsibility, redistribution of material resources and time budget takes place in relations between spouses. Unity of interests, as well as full mutual understanding between spouses may not yet develop. However, there is a reason to eliminate national specific quarrels, the general, international attitude of spouses towards themselves and others, the correct assessment of ethnic "deficiencies" and misunderstandings, if they arise, common views on child rearing, necessary conditions are created for his future cultural adaptation in the surrounding poly-ethnic world.

Young people of different nationalities fall in love with each other and want to get married, and they do not think seriously about the difficulties of living together (including inter-ethnic) that await them in the future.

If, before the wedding, young people lived in neighboring places of residence of representatives of different nationalities, the problems will certainly be solved faster.

The redistribution of social roles, the disappearance of the source of disagreement, the determination of the leader in each function of the family (if it was not previously established according to national traditions) is a very important moment in the life of a large family. This period is also difficult due to problems related to raising children. For representatives of some ethnic communities, this is aggravated by the lack of contact between fathers and children, and for others, on the contrary, it is relieved by the national traditions of the head of the family's active participation in the formation of the inner

world of his children, their upbringing. If the spouses are representatives of different ethnic communities, joint participation in raising children will only help to strengthen their relationship and reduce differences in ethnic traditions.

The national characteristics of family relationships determine the difficulties associated with the fact that these relationships are significantly different from relationships in families where the spouses are representatives of the same nationality.

In addition, there is a certain lack of information about what is happening in family relationships, shortcomings, disagreements among representatives of certain ethnic communities. People are often more secretive here (due to strictness or even the unusual nature of national traditions). Human relations always include interaction, conflict of characters, interests, needs, desire to impose one's views, judgments, values on another. A similar situation is common in family relationships. Marriage is made to mutually satisfy various needs, and only partial or complete satisfaction of some can lead to quarrels and chronic conflicts that destroy the family.

The causes of family conflicts can be seen in the following, that is, they can be as follows:

- stronger or weaker - depending on the traditions in which spouses belonging to representatives of different ethnic communities were brought up;
- unique in the forms of appearance and flow, because specific interactions suitable for one or another ethnic environment leave their mark on them;
- easier or more difficult to regulate, because each nation produces and accumulates experience in solving such problems;
- especially when it comes to families with very specific family traditions and couples of different nationalities.

Modern psychology uses various bases to classify marital conflicts: unsatisfied needs of spouses, inappropriate division of labor, etc. Disputes in family relations on national grounds are sometimes classified according to the needs of the spouses:

- conflicts arising on the basis of an unsatisfied need for self-esteem, violation of dignity by the partner, contempt, disrespect (these conflicts are especially the case when the spouses are representatives of different nationalities, psychological and traditional differences are significant, sometimes strong in discordant families);

- conflicts, quarrels, psychological tensions caused by the unsatisfied sexual needs of one or both spouses (there is a great national specificity of sexual relations that cannot always satisfy spouses of different nationalities);
- quarrels due to psychological dissatisfaction, depression, unsatisfied need for positive emotions of one or both spouses: due to lack of love, care, attention, understanding, because the representatives clearly and quickly see the signs of attention of the husband to his wife “there are peoples who do not show it, for example, in the families of some peoples in the Caucasus, and the Bashkirs - on the contrary);
- disputes, quarrels, gambling based on the alcohol addiction of one of the spouses, which leads to ineffective spending of family funds;
- financial disagreements based on the conflicting needs of the spouses in the distribution of the family budget, the contribution of each to the financial support of the joint life;
- disagreements, quarrels based on the dissatisfaction of the spouses’ needs in material interests: food, clothing, arranging the house;
- disputes based on the need for cooperation in mutual assistance, mutual support, division of labor in the family, management of the household, child care;
- conflicts, disagreements, quarrels arising from differences in the needs and interests of recreation and free time.

The above points show that the psychological conditions for the stabilization of family relations often promote the need to understand, respect and observe the national traditions of each of the spouses, taking into account the psychological characteristics of representatives of different nationalities. Making and explaining, as well as the struggle against attempts to degrade their dignity and national identity, is often carried out at the state and family level.

References:

1. Abduraxmanova Z.E. Oilaviy munosabatlar psixologiyasi. O’quv qo’llanma. Toshkent.”Universitet”.2023 y.
2. Abduraxmanova Z.E. “Millatlararo nikohlarni o’rganishga fenomenologik yondashuv”. International Journal of Economy and Innavaion. SJIF 2023: 7.916
3. Дружинин В.Н. Психология семьи. - СПб: Питер, 2012. 176 с
4. Михайлова А.В., Попова Л.Н. Феноменологический подход к изучению межнациональных браков //Международный журнал прикладных и фундаментальных исследований. – 2016. – № 10-3. – С. 473-477.
5. Соловев Н.Я. Брак и семья сегодня. Вилнюс: Минтис, 2010. 226 с.